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ISSUES OF MODERN ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND THE USE OF INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES

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Annotation. *This article analyzes priority aspects, features and specific aspects of the development of environmental education from developed foreign state Higher Education and other educational institutions.*

Key words: *ecology, environmental education, need, Nature, Natural Resources, hydroecologist, geoecologist, phytoecologist, zoocologist, demoeologist, environment.*

ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО ОПЫТА В ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ

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Аннотация. *В данной статье проанализированы приоритеты, особенности и особенности развития экологического образования в развитых зарубежных государственных высших учебных заведениях и других образовательных учреждениях.*

Ключевые слова: *экология, эколог воспитание, экстирей, природа, природные ресурсы, гидроэколог, геоэколог, фитоэколог, зооэколог, демоэколог, эколог, окружающая среда.*

In today's era of globalization, the natural, social, economic situation that is happening in the world seems more taxing and taxidical than in any period. In particular, the relationship between nature and society has over the centuries brought its influence against each other with oppression, sometimes with an extenuating atmosphere. By the 21st century, this relationship seems to have literally reached a state of disrepute to the maximum of its strength and power. While the remarkable aspect, the quantitative increase of humanity over the centuries, increases the extensibility of nature, but rather the question arises whether natural resources can bear the burden, extensibility of this multibillion-dollar population?

As we know, any state, any nation is powerful not only with its natural resources, but primarily with its high culture and spirituality. Today, it is one of the important tasks that the peoples of the world can show their duty to nature, their devotion to nature, leave the blessings of the greatest and most sacred nature for the future avdod.

In this regard, teaching young people to love and appreciate nature, to preserve the riches of nature should occupy one of the main places in the modern educational system. The formation of environmental knowledge, consciousness and culture in the growing younger generation, the effective organization of the process of environmental education and education today is more important than ever.

Fundamental primary environmental education for the future generation has a central place in preserving nature and ensuring its protection. Monand to international standards, environmental education has its education about the environment, with the help of the environment and for the environment. These three components provide a whole solution to the fragmented issues of environmental education and education. For example, in Western Europe, environmental education and upbringing begins at the age of three, through the communication of children with wild and domestic animals on special farms, and even their care [2].

It is also very important to study the experiences of foreign countries in terms of further improvement and improvement of environmental education. For example, let's pay attention to the experiences of the United States:

In this state, it is noticeable that environmental education is carried out on the basis of various forms, directions, methodological approaches. The important thing is that the ideas of environmental decency, as important moral values, are instilled in the content of all natural and Social Sciences, the involvement of the public in the protection of nature is distinguished in an extraordinary way by the fact that it is organized at the highest level. Especially noteworthy are the activity of non-governmental, non-profit organizations in the process of careful, responsible treatment

of the environment in young people, avaricious preservation of Natural Resources, conscious attitude to legal norms and the formation of an ecological culture.

In American higher education, several aspects of teaching environmental science and training professionals are a special focus. For example, when supplying personnel in the higher education system, it is important to order the customer organization whether it is a state or a non-governmental organization. It is taken into account by the institution in which area the listener or the student who receives the specialty is interested in conducting activities in the field of the environment and is able to fulfill the qualification requirements for it. The general attitude of the student towards the environment, his vision, interest in a particular component of nature and his intellectual and fundamental ideas are considered important. For example, if the worldview of a water resource conservation student is well formed, this in turn is directed to specific activities on Sox, such as a hydroecologist, a similar geocologist, a phytoecologist, a zooecologist, a demoecologist.

In the United States, there is no single universal policy in the field of environmental education, multilateral decisions on environmental education issues are made on the scale of individual states or individual educational institutions.

It is also worth studying, taking a lesson in excellent experiments in the field of environmental education in the Russian Federation. For example, in this state, each federal subject carries out environmental education in its territory in accordance with the law of its territory "on Environmental Education".

As the five main pillars of Confucian ethics in China, qualities such as goodness, correctness, purity, wisdom and reliability are defined and practiced. The environmental education of young people was founded on the idea of "serving and being faithful to the motherland." Young people are taught to keep personal and national interests in harmony and to protect the environment and use natural resources wisely.

Also, in South Korea, on the basis of a national idea, youth is instilled in environmental consciousness through customs, moral ideals. In preparing young people for life, we can see that special attention is paid to family, preschool education, including maintaining the proportion between young people and nature.

In Germany, environmental education is carried out on the basis of a parliamentary approved training plan, ecology and Environmental Protection Sciences are taught as a general compulsory subject in all specialties. It is important that the theory, methodology and practice of environmental education differ from each other in different countries, even in different oases of the same country. The main task, uniting the diversity of rich experiments in environmental education, is of great importance

that these valuable experiments are carried out by the public of all world countries, especially in our country.

In Austria, special programs are included in the transportation of the ground to professional environmental education and education. For example, the creation of a state-owned data bank on environmental education issues in accordance with this program, the implementation of coordination functions, ensuring the participation of young specialists in various projects related to environmental education. At the stage of higher professional education in Austria, environmental education begins directly with the competitive teaching of special and professional subjects.

In Sweden, environmental education and training was followed in 1970 by the preparation and adoption of a national programme on environmental issues. According to its requirements, new teaching aids and guidelines for educators and students were published in Sweden. Environmental education and nurture became a primary issue in the cooperation of the European countries located on the Scandinavian Peninsula. In cooperation with the Swedish society for Environmental Protection and the National Agency for Education, a comprehensive information system on environmental education problems was created [1].

Ireland's environmental education and training is aimed at addressing the following issues: helping to explain the complexities of human-environmental engagement; encouraging interest in economic, social, political and environmental relations in urban and rural areas; giving each listener the knowledge, attitude, value and competence to make responsible environmental decisions, and the necessary practical knowledge and skills to protect and improve the natural environment; in the individual, group and collective consciousness, it is considered to create and put into practice new environmental models for the functioning and behavior of atrophytes, to help the formation of a new attitude to nature in individual citizens, various social groups and communities; to help the population obtain broad practical environmental qualifications; to identify and classify environmental problems, to solve problematic issues and situations, to participate

As can be seen from the above and foreign experience, the introduction into practice of norms that strictly define a truly ecological culture, a serious attitude to the environment, can ensure the achievement of the intended goal in young people in the future.

In summary, first of all, the "concept for the development of Environmental Education" adopted by Uzbekistan on May 27, 2019, for our republic and people, benihoya has become of great importance and one of the most relevant priority areas of Ecology and Environmental Protection; secondly, the development of

environmental education was emphasized by the state as one of the dominant directions, both political, economic, legal and organizational; thirdly, opportunities were created in the field of environmental education to study the rich experiences of foreign countries and apply it in different countries of Uzbekistan; fourth, special attention was paid to the potential of scientists of Uzbekistan, research and implementation of environmental problems; fifth, the technical regulations necessary to fulfill environmental requirements were developed and introduced into life; sixth, special programs for the development of environmental education in our republic, settlements have been created, are funded by the state; seventh, a scientific, conceptual approach to environmental protection was formed [2].

It is undeniable that the above positive circumstances are the fruit of the concept of developing environmental education in our republic, and on the basis of this concept, it is never necessary that it is an honorable duty of every government agency, public organizations, every citizen to raise environmental education to higher levels, to rationally use, preserve, protect and provide environmental security.

LITERATURE USED

1. The” concept for the development of Environmental Education”adopted by Uzbekistan on May 27, 2019
2. M.Abdullayeva, G.Maqsudova. Foreign experience in environmental education and education. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. Volume 1.
3. X.Nazarov. Development of environmental education: problems and solutions. Journal of innovations in scientific and educational research. Volume6 issue-5.
4. Isakulova J. N. Theory and practice of environmental education in students //Monograph. Organization: Science. – 2011.
5. Isakulova N.J. Theory and practice of providing Interdisciplinary Environmental Education to students in the process of continuing education. Dissertation authorization provided for obtaining the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. – 2012.
6. Vergeles G.I., Rayev A.I. Indicators of readiness for professional pedagogical activity.Training (structure and content) // Education, 1994. 5. Grebeshock O.S. Problems of formation of motivation for study and work among students of secondary special vocational education schools: didactic aspect. – M.: Pedagogy, 1985. – 151 p.